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Exports of Goods and Services to Europe

Between 2010 and 2021 they grew by 65.4% equal to 3 trillion euros

Eurostat calculates the value of European countries' exports. The figure is expressed in millions of euros.

Ranking of countries by value of exports in million euros in 2021. Germany ranks first in value of exports in million euros in 2021 with a value of 1,693,923.00, followed by France with a value of 736,475 million euros, and from the Netherlands with a value of 710,604 million euros. In the middle of the table are Finland equal to a value of 99,081 million euros, followed by Romania with a value equal to 98,100 million euros and Slovakia with a value equal to 92,415.90 million euros. Albania closes the ranking with a value of 4,725.90 million euros, followed by Kosovo with a value of 2,685.70 million euros, and Montenegro with a value of 2,122.50 million euros. From the point of view of the concentration of exports, it appears that Germany exports around 20.46% of the total value of European exports, followed by France which exports 8.89%, the Netherlands which exports 8.5%, from Italy with 7% and from Ireland with 6.9%. It follows that Germany, France, the Netherlands, Italy, and Ireland, i.e., 5 countries, exported around 51.9% of total European exports in 2021.

Ranking of European countries by the value of the percentage change in the value of exports in million euros between 2010 and 2021. Ireland ranks first in the value of the percentage change in exports in million euros with a value of 231.55 % equal to an amount of 400,168.20 million euros, followed by Kosovo with a value equal to 204.37% equal to 1,785.20 million euros, and by Serbia with a value equal to 185.55% equal to an amount of 18,880.20 million euros. In the middle of the rankings there are Montenegro with a value equal to 83.34% equal to an amount of 964.8 million euros, followed by Croatia with a value equal to 83.05% equal to 13,552.30 million euros, followed by from Slovakia for a value equal to 75.54% equal to an amount of 39,768.40 million euros. France closes the ranking with a value equal to 37.79% equal to an amount of 201,971 million euros, followed by Finland for a value equal to 37.09% equal to an amount of 26,807 million euros and by Norway for a value equal to 31.61% equal to an amount of 40,694.40 million euro.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The application of the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient highlights the presence of three clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: Bulgaria, Lithuania, Slovenia, Croatia, Serbia, Estonia, Malta, Latvia, Cyprus, Iceland, Greece, Bosnia, North Macedonia, Albania, Montenegro, Kosovo, Romania, Slovakia, Portugal, Finland, Hungary, Luxembourg, Czech Republic, Norway, Denmark, Turkey, Austria, Sweden, Poland.
- Cluster 2: Italy, the Netherlands, Switzerland, France, Spain, Belgium, Ireland;
- Cluster 3: Germany.

From the point of view of the median, the following arrangement results, ie $C3 > C2 > C1$.

Network Analysis with Manhattan distance. A network analysis using the Manhattan distance is presented below. The following complex network structure is detected:

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- North Macedonia has a connection with Bosnia for a value equal to 0.0075 units, with Montenegro for a value equal to 0.029 units, with Iceland for a value equal to 0.028 units, with Albania for a value equal to 0.015 units;
- Bosnia has a connection with North Macedonia equal to a value of 0.0075 units, with Iceland for a value equal to 0.21 units, with Albania for a value equal to 0.021;
- Montenegro has a connection with North Macedonia equal to a value of 0.29 units, with Kosovo with a value equal to 0.002 units, and with Albania equal to a value equal to 0.014 units;
- Albania has a connection with Kosovo for a value equal to 0.016 units, with Bosnia for a value equal to 0.021 units and with Montenegro equal to a value equal to 0.014 units;
- Kosovo has a connection with Albania for a value equal to 0.016 units, with Montenegro for a value equal to 0.002 units;
- Iceland has a connection with North Macedonia worth 0.028, with Bosnia worth 0.021.

The following complex network structure is detected, namely;

- Serbia has a connection with Latvia with a value of 0.22 units, with Estonia with a value of 0.02 units, with Malta with a value of 0.015 units;
- Estonia has a connection with Serbia for a value of 0.02 units, with Latvia for a value of 0.017 units, with Malta for a value of 0.02 units;
- Latvia has a connection with Serbia with a value of 0.022, with Estonia with a value of 0.017, with Malta with a value of 0.012 and with Cyprus with a value of 0.017;
- Malta has a connection with Serbia worth 0.015 units, with Estonia worth 0.12 units with Latvia worth 0.012 units, with Cyprus worth 0.19 unit;
- Cyprus has a connection with Latvia with a value of 0.017 units and with Malta with a value of 0.019 units.

There is a complex network structure between Bulgaria, Lithuania and Slovenia namely:

- Lithuania has a connection with Bulgaria worth 0.022;
- Bulgaria has a connection with Lithuania worth 0.022 and with Slovenia worth 0.017;
- Slovenia has a connection with Bulgaria worth 0.017 units.

Finally, there is a simplified network structure that connects Portugal and Slovakia equal to a value of 0.016 units.

Conclusions. The value of exports grew between 2010 and 2021 by an amount equal to about 64.5%. However, during the covid there was a significant reduction equal to a value of -9.7% equal to approximately 756 billion euros. Between 2010 and 2021, the value of exports grew by 3 trillion euros, reaching the amount of 8 trillion euros. From a quantitative point of view, it should be noted that Germany accounts for 20% of European exports. Furthermore, the Netherlands and Ireland, despite being small countries, manage to export high values. Indeed, the Netherlands and Ireland are in the top five of the largest European exporting countries. However, it must be considered that the mix of inflation, rising energy prices, the Russo-Ukrainian war and Sino-American tension can have a very negative impact on exports of goods and services. A contraction in exports is therefore likely, even if lower than that relating to the covid.

Declarations

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References

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Exports of Goods and Services in European Countries in the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Estimation and Machine Learning Prediction of Imports of Goods in European Countries in the Period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, e-ISSN.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Exports of Knowledge Intensive Services. A Complex Metric Approach (No. 113348). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Export of Medium and High-Tech Products in Europe. University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2022). The Export of High Knowledge Intensity Services of European Countries (No. 112795). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. University Library of Munich, Germany.

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). GDP Growth Rate in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7366715>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). GDP at Constant Prices in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7366771>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Labor Productivity in OECD Countries. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7366797>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Perception of the Financial Situation of European Consumers. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7366993>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Evaluation of the Current Production Capacity of Industry in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7367041>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Imports as a Percentage of GDP in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7369318>

Appendix

Ranking dei paesi per valore delle esportazioni nel 2021 in milioni di euro. Fonte: Eurostat

Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	Germany	1.693.923,00	20	Slovakia	92.415,90
2	France	736.475,00	21	Portugal	89.207,30
3	Netherlands	710.604,00	22	Greece	74.257,70
4	Italy	582.192,40	23	Lithuania	45.219,80
5	Ireland	572.988,00	24	Slovenia	43.661,60
6	Switzerland	483.023,20	25	Bulgaria	43.588,80
7	Belgium	436.322,70	26	Croatia	29.871,50
8	Spain	421.592,00	27	Serbia	29.055,50
9	Poland	332.854,20	28	Estonia	24.620,30
10	Sweden	244.443,30	29	Malta	22.130,60
11	Türkiye	243.430,70	30	Latvia	21.386,90
12	Austria	227.038,40	31	Cyprus	20.804,40
13	Denmark	200.881,50	32	Bosnia and Herzegovina	8.578,00
14	Czechia	173.274,60	33	Iceland	8.271,00
15	Norway	169.421,20	34	North Macedonia	7.736,40
16	Luxembourg	152.855,90	35	Albania	4.725,90
17	Hungary	125.385,80	36	Kosovo	2.658,70
18	Finland	99.081,00	37	Montenegro	2.122,50
19	Romania	98.100,80			

C3>C2>C1

Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Ireland</i>	400.168,20	231,55	20	<i>Slovakia</i>	39.768,40	75,54
2	<i>Kosovo</i>	1.785,20	204,37	21	<i>Czechia</i>	69.768,50	67,41
3	<i>Serbia</i>	18.880,20	185,55	22	<i>Portugal</i>	35.199,60	65,18
4	<i>North Macedonia</i>	4.908,00	173,53	23	<i>Switzerland</i>	189.652,00	64,65
5	<i>Lithuania</i>	27.294,30	152,27	24	<i>Denmark</i>	78.027,20	63,51
6	<i>Romania</i>	57.470,00	141,44	25	<i>Netherlands</i>	264.428,00	59,27
7	<i>Poland</i>	188.899,00	131,22	26	<i>Belgium</i>	160.880,70	58,41
8	<i>Bulgaria</i>	24.405,10	127,22	27	<i>Germany</i>	602.374,00	55,19
9	<i>Latvia</i>	11.833,70	123,87	28	<i>Hungary</i>	44.463,70	54,95
10	<i>Bosnia and Herzegovina</i>	4.726,80	122,74	29	<i>Iceland</i>	2.898,00	53,94
11	<i>Estonia</i>	13.557,20	122,54	30	<i>Greece</i>	25.402,90	52
12	<i>Luxembourg</i>	83.862,50	121,55	31	<i>Spain</i>	143.206,00	51,44
13	<i>Malta</i>	11.842,40	115,11	32	<i>Austria</i>	75.355,40	49,68
14	<i>Cyprus</i>	11.008,70	112,38	33	<i>Sweden</i>	77.033,80	46,02
15	<i>Türkiye</i>	119.475,60	96,39	34	<i>Italy</i>	178.179,40	44,1
16	<i>Albania</i>	2.208,70	87,74	35	<i>France</i>	201.971,00	37,79
17	<i>Slovenia</i>	20.288,80	86,81	36	<i>Finland</i>	26.807,00	37,09
18	<i>Montenegro</i>	964,8	83,34	37	<i>Norway</i>	40.694,40	31,61
19	<i>Croatia</i>	13.552,30	83,05				

	2021	Feature 1	Cluster	Silhouette
1	436322.7	Belgium	C2	0.636219
2	43588.8	Bulgaria	C1	0.726694
3	173274.6	Czechia	C1	0.695862
4	200881.5	Denmark	C1	0.684984
5	1693923.0	Germany	C3	0.5
6	24620.3	Estonia	C1	0.726362
7	572988.0	Ireland	C2	0.549617
8	74257.7	Greece	C1	0.724292
9	421592.0	Spain	C2	0.656539
10	736475.0	France	C2	0.664306
11	29871.5	Croatia	C1	0.726586
12	582192.4	Italy	C2	0.686069
13	20804.4	Cyprus	C1	0.725927
14	21386.9	Latvia	C1	0.726183
15	45219.8	Lithuania	C1	0.726689
16	152855.9	Luxembourg	C1	0.713661
17	125385.8	Hungary	C1	0.714458
18	22130.6	Malta	C1	0.726218
19	710604.0	Netherlands	C2	0.681212
20	227038.4	Austria	C1	0.650744
21	332854.2	Poland	C1	0.610646
22	89207.3	Portugal	C1	0.72211
23	98100.8	Romania	C1	0.723013
24	43661.6	Slovenia	C1	0.726643
25	92415.9	Slovakia	C1	0.722137
26	99081.0	Finland	C1	0.719881
27	244443.3	Sweden	C1	0.63074
28	8271.0	Iceland	C1	0.724836
29	169421.2	Norway	C1	0.691934
30	483023.2	Switzerland	C2	0.670231
31	2122.5	Montenegro	C1	0.72323
32	7736.4	North Macedonia	C1	0.724159
33	4725.9	Albania	C1	0.723726
34	29055.5	Serbia	C1	0.726336
35	243430.7	Türkiye	C1	0.66102
36	8578.0	Bosnia and Her...	C1	0.724345
37	2658.7	Kosovo	C1	0.723187

C1

C2

